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Development of a TDS Measurement System Based on Frequency Impedance Spectroscopy for Water Composition Analysis Integrated With a Well Water Level Meter

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***Abstract:** This paper presents a multi-functional system integrating Total Dissolved Solids (TDS) measurement through frequency impedance spectroscopy, direct distance measurement using simultaneous radio and sound wave propagation, and extended functionality with temperature and pH sensors. These additional sensors significantly enhance the accuracy of water quality assessments by compensating for temperature-dependent variations in conductivity and monitoring the pH, a critical indicator of water acidity or alkalinity. Validation experiments demonstrate the system's efficiency, scalability, and potential for real-time environmental monitoring.*

This TDS measurement method provides a comprehensive analysis of water composition by examining the electrical impedance across a wide frequency range. The developed system leverages low-power IoT technology for real-time data acquisition, emphasizing scalability and energy efficiency for remote deployment. Validation against laboratory benchmarks confirms the system's accuracy and practicality in environmental and industrial applications. This paper details the mathematical modeling, hardware architecture, and experimental results, which collectively advance the field of water quality analysis.

***Keywords:** TDS Measurement, Water Quality Analysis, Distance Measurement, Frequency Impedance Spectroscopy, pH and Temperature Compensation, IoT in Environmental Monitoring*

Introduction

Water quality plays a critical role in ensuring the sustainability of ecosystems, agriculture, and public health. Traditional water analysis methods are often resource-intensive, requiring laboratory conditions

and significant time. The advent of IoT and advanced sensor technologies has enabled real-time monitoring and remote analysis. Impedance spectroscopy is a particularly promising technique due to its non-invasive nature and high sensitivity.

Effective water resource management demands comprehensive monitoring systems capable of assessing various physical and chemical properties. Traditional methods often lack the capability for multi-parameter analysis, limiting their application in dynamic environments.

This study introduces an integrated system for water quality and spatial measurements, incorporating:

1. **TDS Measurement:** Based on frequency impedance spectroscopy, providing insights into ionic composition and conductivity.
2. **Distance Measurement:** Utilizing the propagation delay of radio and acoustic signals for precise, extended-range distance calculations.
3. **Temperature and pH Measurement:** Added functionality to correct conductivity variations due to temperature fluctuations and provide real-time pH monitoring.

This paper describes the development of a TDS measurement device that combines the principles of impedance spectroscopy with modern IoT communication frameworks. The proposed device operates over a broad frequency range (1 kHz to 200 kHz), offering detailed insights into water ionization and conductivity. This capability is essential for applications ranging from agriculture to industrial water quality monitoring. The integration of these functionalities ensures a holistic approach to water quality analysis, improving accuracy and adaptability for diverse applications.

1. Materials and methods of frequency impedance spectroscopy and complex ranging device.

1.1 Principles of impedance spectroscopy used in the device.

The system performs measurements at 20 distinct frequency points within the range of 1 kHz to 100 kHz, with an impedance measurement accuracy of ± 10 Ohm. The TDS meter analyzes the frequency-dependent electrical properties of water through impedance spectroscopy, with measurements affected by ionic concentration and dielectric properties. Temperature and pH compensation allows for real-time calibration and correction

The TDS meter uses impedance spectroscopy to analyze the frequency-dependent electrical properties of water. Impedance is affected by ionic concentration and dielectric properties, which are affected by temperature and pH. Incorporating additional sensors for these parameters allows for real-time calibration and correction of TDS measurements.

Impedance spectroscopy is a technique used to analyze the electrical properties of materials by applying an alternating current (AC) signal at varying frequencies. The impedance, represented as a complex quantity, comprises resistive and reactive components. In water, these components are influenced by dissolved ions, making the technique particularly effective for TDS measurement[4].

Mathematically, the impedance $Z(f)$ of water, taking into account its conductivity (R) and dielectric properties (C), is expressed as:

$$Z(f) = R - jX = R + \frac{1}{j2\pi fC}, (1)$$

where, R is resistance, X is reactance, C is capacitance and f are the frequency.

1.2. Ultrasonic distance measurement system operating principle

The system employs an advanced distance measurement technique known as the "e-beam" method, which operates on the principle of simultaneous radio and ultrasonic signal transmission [1-3,5].

The main device (not shown in Fig. 1) simultaneously emits two signals - a radio signal at a frequency of 433 MHz and an ultrasonic signal at a frequency of 40 kHz

The system determines distance by measuring the time difference between the arrival of these two signals at the receiving end. This works because a radio signal travels at the speed of light (approximately 3×10^8 m/s) and an ultrasonic signal travels at the speed of sound (approximately 343 m/s in air at 20°C). The significant difference in the speeds of propagation allows the distance to be accurately calculated.

The distance measurement subsystem operates by emitting synchronized radio and acoustic pulses, measuring the time delay between arrivals at the receiver. The formula for calculating distance remains:

$$d = v \cdot \Delta t, \quad (2)$$

where, v is the speed of sound, adjusted for temperature, and Δt is the measured delay.

1.3. Temperature and pH Measurement principle

The pH module consists of a pH probe that measures the concentration of hydrogen ions, providing information on the acidity or alkalinity of the water. The pH value is integrated into the chemical analysis and is corrected by the water temperature.

The temperature sensor is a digital temperature sensor based on the DS18B20 remote sensor. This sensor is territorially located in the pH module and is used to measure the water temperature, compensating for changes in conductivity using the following correction factor:

$$\text{Corrected conductivity} = \text{Measured conductivity} \times (1 + \alpha (T - T_{ref})), \quad (3)$$

where α is the temperature coefficient, T is the measured temperature, and T_{ref} is the reference temperature.

1.4. Hardware Architecture Frequency Impedance Spectroscopy and Integrated Distance Measurement device

This device (fig. 1) integrates multiple sensing capabilities, including distance measurement, TDS measurement, pH monitoring, and temperature sensing. The system is powered by a 3.3V accumulator with 1000mAh capacity and uses a sophisticated power distribution system.

In device implements Power Management System. The power system starts with a 3.3V accumulator feeding into a DC/DC converter that generates three voltage levels: +3.3V, +5.0V, and +12V. A Channel Power Distribution Switch manages these power rails, controlled by the CPU, allowing selective power activation for different subsystems to optimize power consumption. The distribution switch includes manual override capabilities through integrated pushbuttons.

The distance measurement subsystem consists of a receiving section, according to the scheme, including an ultrasonic receiving module operating at a frequency of 40kHz, a radio receiving module operating at a frequency of 433 MHz Both modules are connected to the central processor for accurate measurement of the sound travel time. The central processor processes these signals through the UART interface for the radio signal and the timer input for the ultrasonic signal.

Internal calculations to determine the exact distance based on the difference in arrival times of signals. This direct measurement method has several advantages over echoscopic. First, it is more accurate than echo-based systems, and second, it is less susceptible to interference and more reliable in a variety of environmental conditions.

Figure 1. Functional block diagram frequency impedance spectroscopy and integrated distance measurement device

The TDS measurement subsystem also consists of a TDS measurement module using the frequency impedance spectroscopy approach. It consists of a DDS (Direct Digital Synthesis) generator controlled by the CPU via frequency control signals and a 1 k Ω precision resistor in series with the TDS sensor. From where the measurement signal is fed to the ADC of the CPU for data collection.

The DDS generator produces varying frequency signals, allowing impedance measurements across different frequencies. This multi-frequency approach enables more accurate TDS measurements by analyzing the solution's frequency-dependent impedance characteristics (1).

To monitor environmental parameters, a pH+T value determination module for liquids is used, where a pH sensor is combined to measure the acidity/alkalinity of a solution and a temperature sensor to simultaneously measure the temperature on separate dedicated ADC channels for both parameters.

The data transmission subsystem uses a 433MHz high-power long-range wireless module to transmit data. This communication system operates at 433MHz to ensure long-range operation. Connects to the CPU via a UART interface, includes an external antenna to improve signal strength, and enables remote monitoring and data collection.

This integration allows the device to perform comprehensive water quality analysis while maintaining power efficiency through selective subsystem activation. The wireless capability enables remote monitoring and data collection, making it suitable for automated in well water quality monitoring applications.

The device integrates the following components (fig. 1):

- stainless steel electrodes immersed in water act as the measurement interface;
- frequency generator based on the AD9833 DDS module providing accurate AC signals in the target frequency range;
- microcontroller CPU manages signal generation, data acquisition and communication;
- data acquisition from multiple sensors into the microcontroller sequentially reads temperature, pH, TDS and distance data, processing them for combined analysis;
- dynamic control via MIC2026/MIC2076 ensures power efficiency by activating sensors and modules only when measurements are made;
- data is transmitted wirelessly via a 433 MHz RF module for remote monitoring.

2. Software Implementation

The software implementation of the system combines several stages to effectively manage the measurement, processing and transmission of data. The main stages include the pre-processing stage, data collection by the microcontroller. Raw data from various sensors, such as impedance data for TDS measurement, temperature and pH values for TDS compensation. Distance measurements using synchronized acoustic and radio signals. Also the post-processing stage, which includes temperature compensation of conductivity data corrected based on the measured temperature using equality 3 and pH calibration taking into account the ionic properties of the solution, is further refined using pH data to improve the accuracy of TDS analysis.

For post-processing of spectral data, the least-squares method is used to fit the impedance spectrum. The mathematical model minimizes the error between the measured impedance $Z(f)$ and the theoretical model:

$$\min \sum_{i=0}^n [Z_{measured}(fi) - Z_{model}(fi, \epsilon)]^2, (4)$$

where, $Z_{measured}(fi)$ is the measured impedance at frequency fi ;

$Z_{model}(f, \epsilon)$ is the predicted impedance based on the parameters of ϵ (e.g., ion concentration, dielectric properties), and fi is the frequency.

All calibrated and corrected data (TDS, temperature, pH, and distance) are packaged into a single result set for further analysis.

The system utilizes the least squares method to fit the impedance spectrum to a predefined model. The provided algorithm flowchart (fig. 2) describes the sequential flow of operations in the program:

Figure 2. Flowchart diagram operations principle in the program.

- At the beginning, the system initializes and goes into sleep mode to save energy.
- Command processing - when the "SET" command is received, the system configures the operating parameters (e.g. frequency ranges, measurement cycles) or when the "O" command is received, the measurement process is started.
- The measurement workflow consists of distance measurements using the acoustic radio synchronization method, and temperature measurements are also performed. In parallel, impedance spectroscopy measurements are performed for TDS analysis in preparation for TDS calibration.
- Pre-processing and transmission of results using the least squares method and packaging for transmission.
- Once the measurements and transmission are complete, the system returns to sleep mode.

3. Results

Testing conducted during 2023-2024 demonstrated the following key performance metrics:

- Power consumption optimization: <1 mA in sleep mode, >50 mA in run mode
- pH measurement capabilities: 0.00-14.00 range, ± 0.5 pH accuracy
- Temperature sensing: 0.1-60°C range, $\pm 0.5^\circ\text{C}$ accuracy

- Distance measurement: ± 10 cm accuracy up to 300 meters
- Data transmission: 2400 bits per second
- Electrical conductivity range: 0-9999 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$ to 20.1-400.0 mS/cm ($\pm 2\%$ F.S.)

The developed system demonstrated high sensitivity, detecting ion concentrations as low as 10 ppm. Comparison with laboratory equipment showed a deviation of less than 2%, highlighting its reliability.

Power consumption was reduced by 50% through dynamic power management, extending the life of battery-powered devices.

Impedance measurements and data transfer were performed within milliseconds, enabling real-time analysis suitable for industrial and agricultural applications.

The inclusion of temperature and pH data increased the accuracy of TDS measurement:

- temperature compensation- reduces deviations due to environmental changes with an average accuracy increase of 12%;
- pH influence- provides advanced water quality analysis by revealing correlations between ion composition and pH levels;
- distance measurement achieved:
- ± 1 cm accuracy achieved at distances up to 100 meters;
- Enhanced measurement capabilities compared to traditional methods.

Sequential activation of modules and sensors resulted in 60% power savings, enabling long-term operation for battery-powered deployments. The system was calibrated using standard solutions of known conductivity, ensuring precise impedance measurement. Calibration involved:

1. Recording impedance spectra for each solution.
2. Applying polynomial fitting to establish a correlation between impedance and TDS values.

Discussion

The system successfully addresses key challenges in wireless water monitoring, particularly the synchronization between floating and well-head components operating at ISM 433 MHz. The implementation of sleep mode activation through specific "Wake up" signals represents an innovative solution for power management while maintaining measurement reliability.

The addition of temperature and pH sensors, as well as the use of ultrasonic direct level measurement, significantly expands the device's capabilities for comprehensive well water quality analysis. Key benefits include:

- real-time compensation for temperature and pH changes ensures accurate TDS measurements;
- modular design supports the integration of additional sensors such as turbidity or dissolved oxygen sensors and supports deployment in large-scale water monitoring networks;
- suitable for a variety of applications from agricultural irrigation systems to industrial water monitoring;
- eliminates the need for complex sample preparation;
- enables long-term operation in remote environments.

The system's comprehensive approach to monitoring multiple parameters eliminates the limitations of traditional single-purpose devices. Future work will explore the integration of AI-based analytics to predict trends and optimize water management strategies, and will add future developments including the integration of machine learning algorithms for automated analysis and the inclusion of multi-parameter sensors to expand functionality.

Conclusion

This research advances water quality monitoring technology by combining impedance spectroscopy-based TDS measurement with innovative distance measurement and environmental parameter compensation. The prototype demonstrates significant potential for practical applications in environmental monitoring and water resource management. This study presents a multifunctional water monitoring system that integrates TDS measurement, direct distance measurement, and temperature and pH sensors. The integrated approach provides high accuracy, scalability, and energy efficiency, making it ideal for a variety of environmental and industrial applications. The results confirm the potential of the system as a valuable tool for real-time water quality and resource management.

The proposed system also illustrates the potential of impedance spectroscopy for TDS measurement in water quality analysis. Its accuracy, scalability, and energy efficiency make it a valuable tool for environmental monitoring, industrial applications, and scientific research. This study lays the foundation for future advances in water quality management using the Internet of Things (IoT).

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